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The Magnitude of Development Induced Displacement and Human Rights Violation in Odisha: The Case Study of Dispossessed Tribals of Angul District

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ABSTRACT

Development programs that promote income, education, and health may be viewed as participatory if they do not result in the majority of the population being in a worse state of poverty. By encouraging a large inflow of capital, the government's single-window system, liberalized policies, and strengthened institutions have expedited the state's possibilities for rapid industrialization. The projects whether mining, construction of dams, cities or industries have been projected by the state for raising quality of life of people. Different sectors of society react to this development which paved the way for displacement in many ways, and it also affects people's lives in diverse ways. It not only affects people in general but also marginalized especially tribals. The situation has been aggravated by the initiation of globalization and liberalization process which is harping at the root of the very issue of fundamental human rights over life and land. In this scenario, development is something that brings benefits as well as costs. The biggest cost of this is that millions of vulnerable groups became displaced leading to the collapse of their political, social and cultural lives. It manifests in a number of ways, incorporating social disarray, low self-esteem, identity loss, cultural appropriation, and the breakdown of political institutions. The paper is an attempt to evaluate various implications of displacement on social and cultural aspect of the dispossessed tribals by major industries like NALCO, Jindal Steel & Power Ltd, MCL, NTPC of Angul district of Odisha.

Keywords: *Development, Displacement, Human Rights, Industries, Dispossessed Tribals, Socio-Cultural Spheres*

INTRODUCTION:

The present wave of industrialization and globalization and the power of money and the market have started to erode democracy, and natural resources found in rural and tribal communities are being plundered to satisfy the ever-increasing needs and desires of the privileged group. The administration has made repeated claims about the need for sustainable industrial displacement and the development of tribal and rural people residing close to industrial sites, but they have not been transformed into practical measures. Although there is no denying that the inhabitants in these areas have experienced tremendous economic growth but the harsh reality is that these benefits have resulted in previously

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unheard-of losses to social capital, family, kinship, and caste systems. People, market forces, and the state have long been at the center of the development argument. It has also been noted that while the goal of development project is to alleviate poverty but in reality, they frequently result in the creation of new impoverished areas, which push a significant portion of the population into unemployment as a result of the negative effects of megaprojects on the environment and human population as well as forced relocations. Following independence, the path of socioeconomic development continued and accelerated. The main question is whether to explore for alternatives arising from people's struggles and human rights movements, or to admit important progressive ideas extended by the state as well as market.

Odisha occupies a unique position among different states of India along with union territories due to its colorful tribal environment and they are mostly living in forest areas. Despite experiencing social, educational, and economic regression as a result of geohistorical factors, the Scheduled Tribes of Odisha have preserved their distinct identity and culture.

The Angul District in Odisha has seen significant industrial growth as a result of its advantageous location and large supply of labor and raw resources. NALCO, NTPC, and MCL are the district's three principal power plants. In addition, the district now has a large number of private industries set up in the steel and power sectors. The region's development quest significantly altered the way tribal communities interacted with the natural environment and its resources, leading to the disempowerment of these tribes and negatively affecting marginalized groups. "Out of the entire population in the district, 13.90 percent people are living in urban areas and 86.10 percent in rural areas" (Angul District Vision 2020). "11.6% of the Angul population is made up of schedule tribes, with the greatest concentration of these tribes in the Pallahara block" (Nari Surakya Samiti : 2024).

Industrial activity and Mining in Angul:

Angul is the district that produces the most coal in all of Odisha and talcher region of the district boasts extensive coal mines, while plans are underway to expand the Chhendipada area by increasing the current count of coal mines from one to more than thirty in the coming years."In 2005-06, the value of all minerals in Angul district was Rs.395728lakhs which was highest in the state, and was 39.05% of the total output value of all minerals in Odisha"(Nari Surakya Samiti : 2024). A

major contributor to the district of Angul's overall development is the industrial sector. Six PSUs, listed below, accounted for the majority of the district of Angul's plans and programs up until 2008. Out of the six, there are three large scale industries which have also enhanced their production.

Here are the specifics.

1. Mahanadi Coalfields Limited, Talcher
2. National Thermal Power Station, Talcher
3. Heavy Water plant in Talcher
4. NALCO Smelter Plant, Angul
5. Kaniha Super Thermal Power Station, Talcher
6. Captive Thermal Power Plant, NALCO Angul

Despite these, there are also many private sector industries situated in the region. Large enterprises have led to the creation of some environmental problems. Utilizing fly ash, which is a byproduct generated by power and other similar plants, is not currently being considered. There is currently no long-term option for using the clinker produced in steel plants. Air and water pollution is increasing daily. The waste products pose a hazard to the agriculture sector.

Magnitude of Displacement:

Development is described as the advancement of industry and technology, which serve as the means to an end. It's just another way of social change. But human societies do not always benefit from economic development. The multifaceted character of development interventions has an impact on human societies' socio-cultural, economic, health, and environmental facets. The process of uprooting or forcing groups and individuals to leave their native areas is known as displacement. People are compelled against their will to migrate and resettle at different locations as a result of numerous developmental activities, such as- creation of industries, irrigation, railroads, road developments, sanctuaries, dam construction, and so forth. This is called involuntary resettlement where individuals are forced to migrate or relocate.

Development induced displacement implies forcing people and communities to abandon their residences often from their native lands, in the pursuit of economic advancement. Displacement thus regarded as a necessary cost of development by those who see development as nothing more than economic expansion.

Acceleration of industries paved the way for displacement which posed a major challenge to human

development culminating in creation of mass slum in each industrial city with unclean water, poor electricity connection as well as sanitation (Bhattacharya : 2013). This causes various diseases like typhoid, jaundice, cholera, dysentery, chikungunia, dengue, malaria etc and also exploitation of resources which caused various forms of pollution. The major challenges that human beings are facing- they are deprived of their land, home, job, food, property, they are facing social and economic deprivation, it put negative impact on their health, it caused increase of domestic violence, child labour and insecurity for future generation (Bhattacharya: 2013).

The overall Impact of displacement on tribals that are

- As a cause of displacement, women experience higher rates of unemployment compared to men.
- Displacement accelerates destruction of socio-cultural fabric of tribals and induced extreme poverty on them
- Due to the loss of access to the forest area reduced a traditional medicinal practice undergone by tribal communities

Violation of Human rights:

Many of the world’s poorest people lack access to sufficient and safe housing, despite this being a basic human right. Every human person has the inherent right to human rights, which are fundamental to their social and cultural spheres. They are susceptible to misuse and infringement, nevertheless. The conditions of tribals remain unchanged in India as they are facing violation of basic human rights, brutality, isolation along with social discrimination which paved the way for various tribal movements in India for the protection and promotion of their rights. The constitutional provisions as mentioned in the 5th schedule of the Indian constitution, along with state-level laws aim to prevent the transfer of tribal lands. However, these measures

have not effectively stopped the widespread loss of land among tribal communities. The government is permitted to acquire land for public purposes under the Land Acquisition Act of 1894, which has been the main reason for land alienation. “After the emergence of private property and the emergence of modern nation states, as Tribal communities have no legal rights over the lands they have been living on and cultivating for generations” (Halvath: 2014). Upon the implementation of the Forest Conservation Act of 1980, tribal lands spanning thousands of acres were swiftly invaded. The Scheduled Tribes and Other Traditional Forest Dwellers (Recognition of Forest Rights) Act was passed by the Indian government in 2006 and “the Act is aimed at undoing the age-old injustice done to Tribal communities by restoring and recognizing their pre-existing rights” (Thipper: 2014). The Rules of procedure of the Forest Rights Act were not notified, resulting in continued prosecution of tribal communities.

Tribals, who have been living on the same land for generations, do not have legal rights to it and are facing threats and penalties for entering the forest. In 1996, the Panchayat Extension to the Scheduled Areas (PESA) Act was created which aims to give tribal communities the authority to preserve and advance their cultural heritage and communal assets through Gram Sabha. Despite the rules of the act, no initiatives are taken up at the time of developmental projects to take consent and opinion of Gram Sabha. Different rehabilitation policies considered men as heads of family hence, the domestic power relatively passes fully to men and the patriarchal system continues. It causes women dependence on men’s single income.

A case study of Industrial displacement in Angul:

The following table shows the entire tribal Population living in different blocks of Angul district covering major industrial sites.

Sl. No.	Block Name	Total Gram panchayat	No.of Rural Families	Total nos of Schedule caste population	Total no of Tribal population	Nos. of Below poverty Lane families	% of Below poverty Lane families
1	Angul	32	29533	5241	2696	19748	67
2	Athamalik	24	19543	3022	2872	14204	73
3	Banarpal	25	30904	6244	976	18141	59
4	Chendipada	34	28728	4839	1845	17353	60
5	Kanhia	26	24222	3953	1409	12911	53
6	Kishore nagar	21	18535	2472	3304	14301	77

7	Pallahara	26	26444	3282	7819	17813	67
8	Talcher	21	25243	2042	1190	6109	24
Total		209	20315	3109	2211	120581	59

Source-NariSurakyaSamithi, Angul

National Aluminium Company(NALCO):

The establishment of NALCO's Angul sector, which includes Smelter Riant and Captive Power Plant, came at a cost of US\$1000 million. 3,997 families from 40 villages were impacted by the acquisition of 3,877.81 acres of land in the district. The loss of their land alone had a partial impact on these families. Out of these 40 villages, people from 39 villages lost their agricultural land, and 34 households were completely uprooted, losing both their homestead and their cultivable land. "Its notable efforts include Indradhanush scheme, where the Company has sponsored 920 tribal children of Maoist infested Damanjodi sector and provided education to them in 3 reputed residential schools. 416 meritorious girl students of BPL families at Angul and Damanjodi sector have been adopted with financial support by the Company under 'Nalco ki Ladli' scheme in line with Govt's 'Beti Bachao, Beti Padhao' Mission" (NalcoIndia, 2020).

Government of Odisha's rehabilitation scheme for families displaced by the NALCO complex at Angul and Damanjodi lacks a comprehensive approach to rehabilitation, as it does not include land for land, a principle that has been implemented in other projects involving displacement.

Jindal Steel and Power Plant:

Another instance of the displacement in the district of Angul is caused by Jindal power plant ltd. This is a thermal power plant in the village of Derang of Angul district. The project has displaced about 15,000 residents. The Odisha government initially suppressed the anti-displacement campaign. A public debate supervised by the district administration and held by the State Pollution Control Board, saw people challenging the scheme. "The first hearing was manipulated and fabricated by which the company got environment clearance" (Samantara: 2014). The government obtained about four thousand acres of land for it with the help of police, along with offering significant compensation, and assurances of employment. After acquiring the land, the displaced people are deceived and left without jobs or any means of supporting themselves. When displaced people went

to company gate for redressal of their grievances, they were brutally attacked by the security guards. Another 5000 acres of forest land has been seized by the company, leading to destruction of over 4lakh Sal tree without proper clearance. The affected people have been requesting fair compensation together with rehabilitation. "The government remains silent whereas the people have been waiting for justice"(Samantara: 2014).

The impacted villages have a customary style of rural living centered on agriculture. The main sources of income were wage work, associated industries, harvesting forest products, and agriculture. Their environmentally conscious and adaptable producing practices are so sustainable that they scarcely rely on the secondary sector for food security.

Mahanadi Coalfield Limited & National Thermal Power Corporation:

In the Angul Talcher region of Orissa, the creation of NTPC (National Thermal Power Corporation) and MCL (Mahanadi Coalfields Limited) has had an impact on the natural vegetation, agricultural crops, and social environment. MCL's pay is larger than that of the Odisha State Government, yet it is insufficient to cover rising market prices for housing."In MCL about 16,297 persons have been identified to be displaced, out of which 11,837 have already been provided resettlement benefits"(Ministry of Mines: 2022). "Out of 11,837 families, only 8,248 families have shifted from their respective villages"(Ministry of Mines: 2022). These families are currently processed with resettlement support. The Odisha government's Rehabilitation and Resettlement (R&R) policy dictates the provision of relocation benefits.

"NTPC acquired 3555.28 acres of lands from 53 villages in 1991" (Garada: 2015). "The project acquired local lands and provided rehabilitation and resettlement benefits to both substantially impacted persons (SAPs) who lost 1/3 or more of their total lands and the least affected people"(Garada:2015)."Out of 1591 SAPs 650(40.85%) was identified eligible for plant jobs, however out of these 650 eligible persons only 67.69 percent persons could get jobs in NTPC plant, the rest

were entitled to cash compensation” (Garada:2015). The health risks for the affected villages located near thermal power plants are cumulative and direct.

Remedies to Curtail forced displacement:

- Introduction of comprehensive compensation package
- payment should be made for taking the land,
- a prominent initiative must be taken by financial institutions to motivate displaced people for savings,
- proper educational facilities must be provided to their children by opening schools nearby them,
- adequate health care facilities should be provided at rehabilitation centre,
- there should be proper tackling of poverty and unemployment, care must be undertaken to reduce gender disparities

The entitlements and rights of indigenous people in the Odisha:

Despite the Constitution’s special enabling provisions for them, a legal framework for putting these provisions into practice, and a number of focused public policy initiatives, they have persisted in facing various forms of deprivation and dispossession.

- In the 1997 *Samata v. State of Andhra Pradesh* Judgment, also referred to as the *Samata Judgment*, the law court of India rendered a milestone judgement keeping the rights to livelihood of tribals in the nation’s scheduled territories. In this instance, the judiciary attained the highest level of success in defending the indigenous community’s rights. The core achievement of *Samantha* judgement at the Supreme Court lies in expanding the scope of the word ‘person’ contained in the various regulations, made under the mandate of the fifth schedule . “Any lease to non-tribals even of a Government land situated in scheduled area is in violation of section 3 and so is void”(Mahapatra: 2015).
- “The OSATIP(Orissa Scheduled Area Transfer of Immovable Property by Scheduled Tribes) Regulation, 1956 proved to be insufficient to protect tribal rights, as the law permitted transfer of patta land from tribals to non-tribals after

obtaining permission from mandatory authority, but in such transaction, manipulation was high and innocent tribals often lost their land in dubious transfer”(Ambagudia:2010).

- The Orissa Reforms Act of 1960, in its Section 22 along with 23 safeguard the rights of the indigenous community residing outside of scheduled areas against land alienation. Written consent is required from the revenue officer for transfer of land of tribals to any other entity
- The Odisha government periodically amended Regulation 2 of 1956 to strengthen the rules protecting tribal lands and making sure that the transfer of land to non-tribals in the scheduled area of the state was forbidden.
- “Odisha Government has enacted Orissa Resettlement and Rehabilitation Policy,2006, in order to ensure sustained development through a participatory and transparent Process”(Govt. of Odisha: 2006). The policy aims to prevent displacement wherever feasible, support the resettlement rehabilitation process by acknowledging the input of displaced communities and highlighting the requirements of vulnerable groups, ensure environmental sustainability through transparent and participatory processes, and assist in directing the development of institutional mechanisms for monitoring, implementation, and grievance redress.

CONCLUSION:

The nation’s resources are growing more abundant thanks to coal mining, and the government is making considerable money. However, the detrimental effects—such as pollution of the air, water, and noise—as well as the disruption of social networks, indigenous culture, and patterns of social organization—as well as the decline in health, loss of agricultural productivity, and effects on communities—are not taken into consideration. In addition to making it more difficult to extract coal for our future sustainable energy needs, failing to address these sociological and economic aspects of development would lead to a wide range of social movements that could jeopardize the livelihoods of rural and tribal people. The development process introduces tribals to a new formal economy without proper training. The community relied on agricultural land and forest areas, which are now being lost due to construction initiatives. Most tribal societies in the

informal economy are unfamiliar with monetary compensation, and Common Property Resources (CPRs) are rarely rewarded. Four impacted outcomes are reflected in the total state of people's health in a polluted environment: one is environmental pollution, two is physical pollution, three is mental disturbance, and four is social disruption. Tribal people's dispossession has also been facilitated by laws and policies pertaining to forests. Several forest regulations classify the vast majority of the land in tribal communities as forests. The infrastructural improvements and payment of annuity at the relocated place have caused some resentment among the displaced inhabitants. In order to prevent a vicious circle of vulnerability, the industrial authority should handle this before any physical displacement occurs. There could be social and cultural issues, and there is nothing in R&R Policies that deals with the issues that may occur in the aftermath of displacement.

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AD&DKD was responsible for the first manuscript draft. All authors contributed to subsequent drafts and approved the final version.

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